

Corrigendum

Performance–Efficiency Trade-offs in Anomaly Detection Architectures for Zero-Day IoT Attack Detection: A Systematic Benchmark on CICIoT2023

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After publication, the following errors were identified in the reference list of the above paper. These errors do not affect the technical results, methodology, or conclusions of the paper. This corrigendum is issued to ensure accurate source attribution and citation linking.

Reference [11]

Published as:

M. A. Rahman, A. A. Al-Ghamdi, M. S. Hossain, and G. Muhammad, “A survey on intrusion detection systems in IoT networks,” *Array*, vol. 19, Art. no. 100345, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.array.2024.100345.

Should read:

M. M. Rahman, S. A. Shakil, and M. R. Mustakim, “A survey on intrusion detection system in IoT networks,” *Cyber Security and Applications*, vol. 3, Art. no. 100082, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.csa.2024.100082.

Note: The DOI as published resolves to a different work. The intended reference is the Rahman et al. survey in Cyber Security and Applications.

Reference [12]

Published as:

M. Roopak, A. Ahmed, and F. S. Alenezi, “An unsupervised approach for the detection of zero-day attacks in IoT networks,” *IET Networks*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 257–269, 2024, doi: 10.1049/ntw2.12134.

Should read:

E. Rodríguez, P. Valls, B. Otero, J. J. Costa, J. Verdú, M. A. Pajuelo, and R. Canal, “Transfer-learning-based intrusion detection framework in IoT networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 15, Art. no. 5621, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22155621.

Note: This entry did not correspond to the intended reference and has been replaced.

Reference [16]

Published as:

T. Abdelwahed, A. Derhab, M. Guerroumi, and A. A. Al-Ghamdi, “A survey of IoT multi-protocol gateways: Architectures, challenges, and methodologies,” *ICT Express*, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.ict.2025.101703.

Should read:

S. H. Abdelwahed, I. M. Hefny, M. Hegazy, L. A. Said, and A. Soltan, “Survey of IoT multi-protocol

gateways: Architectures, protocols and cybersecurity,” *Internet of Things*, vol. 33, Art. no. 101703, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.iot.2025.101703.

Note: The DOI resolves correctly, but the author list, title, and journal name in the published record do not match the work at that DOI.

Reference [17]

Published as:

A. Paszke et al., “PyTorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library,” in *Proc. 33rd Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. (NeurIPS)*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Dec. 2019, pp. 8026–8037.

Should read:

A. Paszke et al., “PyTorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library,” in *Proc. 33rd Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. (NeurIPS)*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Dec. 2019, pp. 8024–8035.

Note: The official NeurIPS 2019 proceedings list this paper at pp. 8024–8035.

The author apologizes for these errors.

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